

Speculation on Spatial Density and Acceleration

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In a previous note (1), we argued that the classical statistical mechanics of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas is linked (in a canonical distribution sense) to an additive scalar (e_i = kinetic energy of a particle) and leads to $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ if one uses information loss considerations i.e. $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3)$ where a is the additive scalar. We further argued that a quantum particle also satisfies this information loss equation, but with a being a vector such as momentum. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, although an unusual one.

In (2) we argued that a classical equilibrium distribution based on an additive scalar which is linked by a conservation law in space i.e. $a(x_1) + B(x_1) = a(x_2) + B(x_2)$ necessarily introduces a probability factor of the form $\exp(-iB(x)/T)$, but leaves the $\exp(-a_i/T)$ distribution unchanged. We suggested this be interpreted as a spatial density linked to acceleration of particles. In this note, we argue that if both the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ and the classical MB distribution both follow from the same $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3)$ condition, then the notion of density and acceleration should also be found in quantum mechanics, even for $\exp(ipx)$ which represents constant velocity.

Additive Scalar and Vector Statistical Mechanics

In (1) we argued that the seemingly different statistical mechanical schemes, namely the classical MB gas and the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ have the same statistical origin, namely the loss of information condition:

$$P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_3) \quad ((1))$$

where a_i is either an additive scalar or a dynamical vector which appears in a stochastic process in the system. E.g. kinetic energy may appear in two body elastic scattering in an MB gas.

In the case of an additive scalar one has $P(a_i) = C \exp(-a_i/T)$ where T is a parameter fixed by: $\langle a \rangle = \sum_i C \exp(-a_i/T) a_i$. [The form $P(a)$ may be obtained by using $a_1 + a_2 = a_3$ and taking \ln of ((1)) and linking the two or by using $d/d(1/T) P(a_i) = -a_i P(a_i)$.]

In the vector case, one essentially has the same solution, $\exp(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but the vector is " i " times r vector so the overall result is periodic and demonstrates a kind of spatial invariance. Here \mathbf{a} might be \mathbf{p} (momentum). One may note that time is removed when dealing with probabilities here. One may also note that $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of the spatial generator times $-i$ i.e. $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$.

One last point we wish to consider is that: $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ exhibits spatial density in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ does not. We try to interpret this in a later section.

Additive Scalar, X Correlation and Acceleration

The additive scalar solution $C\exp(-a_i/T)$ does not need to be linked with motion i.e. a_i does not need to be kinetic energy. (For example, it could be spin energy in a magnetic field.) As shown in (2), however, if one tries to correlate a_i in space i.e. uses an equation:

$$a_i(x_1) + B(x_1) = a_i(x_2) + B(x_2) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } B(x) \text{ is some function}$$

Then, ((1)) and the idea of the RHS and LHS sides of ((2)) representing the same overall information i.e. the same overall constant suggests that:

$$P(a_i, x) = C_1 \exp(-a_i/T) \exp(-B(x)/T) \quad ((3))$$

(To see this, imagine $B(x_1)=0$.) ((3)) indicates that the a_i distribution is unchanged. In (2), we argued that $\exp(-B(x)/T)$ implies a spatial density which may only be created by having more particles at one place than another. This means the particles cannot be moving at the same constant speed, but should be accelerating and that a_i should be linked to velocity. As a result, a spatial density seems to imply acceleration and such a density naturally arises if one tries to impose x related correlations i.e. create a probability distribution in x . The notion of the same form of a_i distribution at x_1 and x_2 i.e. $\exp(-a_i/T)$ leads to differing spatial densities and acceleration i.e. a force field.

We investigate whether these ideas carry over into dynamical vector statistical scheme i.e. quantum mechanics.

Dynamical Vector, Spatial Density and Acceleration

The idea of (2) is that a correlation of the stochastic variable with position may lead to a distribution in position which demonstrates/defines the correlation. These changes are automatically associated with a change in "density" and hence an acceleration. At first this seems contradictory because for the dynamical vector case where $p=\text{constant}$ momentum vector there is a constant velocity i.e. no acceleration, but:

$\exp(ipx)$ which satisfies ((1)) contains $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which have a spatial density.

How does one deal with this contradiction? One might argue that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which has no spatial distribution. Each point in x has the same weight. (One may note that from a reflection/refraction problem with light, discussed in (1), taking square roots of intensities yields equations which govern the probabilities. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is like this square root.)

The problem with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ is that the same number applies to all constant p vectors as well as to forward and backwards motion. In other words, important information is lost in this scenario, even though it is true that each x point has the same importance, perhaps on

average. We note that $\exp(ipx)$ implies a wavelength of \hbar/p , so for a given p , one cannot subdivide the x axis into smaller units than \hbar/p . If one does so, one really interpolates within such a region, suggesting constant motion on average even though there exists $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ implying different physics.

We note that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ contains no time as does $\exp(ipx)$. In Newtonian mechanics, however, one needs both x and t in order to define a direction of motion. $\exp(ipx)$ has two dimensions to define the direction of motion, but avoid the notion of time. Thus we argue that the densities $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ might be associated with a kind of action-reaction force (acceleration) which on average leads to constant motion. This action-reaction process distinguishes forward and backwards motion i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ differ. If one adds the two, one obtains $2\cos(px)$ which represents a density. The opposite reactions have canceled leaving a density in x . $\cos(px)$ is an eigenfunction of kinetic energy $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$, but not of momentum $-id/dx$. One does not know if one has p or $-p$ (with an acceleration being needed to convert one into the other).

Next we consider $\cos(px)$, or rather $\sin(px)$ as a solution of the infinite well problem with the walls at $x=0$ and $x=L$ and $p=n\pi/L$. In such a case, one notes there is correlation between probability at $x=0$ and $x=L$ (which is called a boundary condition). This means probability at $x=0$ and $x=L$ must be the same, but must be distinguished from other x values. This creates a distribution in x and we argue from (2) suggests the presence of acceleration/force. In this case, the solution is really a superposition of all momentum states defined in all space not just within $x=0$ to $x=L$.

$$\sin(n\pi x/L) \text{ (within } (0,L) = \sum \text{ over } p a(p)\exp(ipx) \text{ over all } x \text{ ((4))}$$

Thus the notion of a mix of p 's or acceleration yielding the x distribution $\sin(px)$ is not so far-fetched even though on average $\sin(px)$ is associated with a constant kinetic energy, but again with $p=n\pi/L$ and $-p$ which already suggests again an acceleration.

Resolution and Acceleration

The notion of resolution depends on a probability distribution in x as is well known i.e. interference. In the case of $\exp(ipx)$, we argue there is a resolution in x space of \hbar/p , but if the idea of spatial density being linked with force/acceleration holds then there is also force in the picture, if even associated with p and $-p$. We suggest the idea of force which appears in Newtonian mechanics and is associated with dp/dt is also linked with a spatial distribution, which in turn is linked with information and probability distributions with correlations in space.

Hand-wavy Notion of Spin

We suggest that if one has a distribution in space with $-p$, p as being linked to a spatial density that a three dimensional quantum object should have $-p, p$ in all directions i.e. be composed of dynamical square root flux terms of $\exp(ipx)$ in all directions. This seems to suggest the possibility of spin motion in all directions (in a handwavy manner). Measuring in one direction and finding spin up or down does not eliminate the idea that a distribution in a

nonmeasured direction does not contain p and $-p$ components if one takes another measurement along a different axis.

Classical Bound System

As another example, consider a classical bound system in one dimension i.e. $.5mv^2 + V(x) = E$. One may subdivide the x axis into equally spaced units. In Newtonian mechanics, one uses the two variables x, t and so dt differs in the various dx units. $V(x)$ is in the form of information and dt is proportional to probability. If the same dt exists at x_1 and some x_2 point, then there is a correlation in space and the other x points must have different dt values i.e. there must be a distribution in space. Such a distribution suggests acceleration which in fact exists. Thus it seems that even in Newtonian mechanics one may use the idea of correlated probabilities in space implying acceleration. (If all x points had the same dt , then there would be constant v i.e. there is no changing spatial distribution i.e. change in information.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is well known that a potential in classical statistical mechanics $V(x)$ creates a spatial density. A potential in Newtonian mechanics, however, implies single particle acceleration. Thus we associate the idea of acceleration with a spatial density. In (2) we showed explicitly that a correlation between a probability distribution is some additive scalar a_i at x_1 and x_2 leads to a factor $P(x) = \exp(-B(x)/T)$ where $a_i(x_1) + B(x_1) = a_i(x_2) + B(x_2)$. The probability distribution in a_i is the same at x_1 and x_2 and so we suggested $\exp(-B(x)/T)$ must imply a spatial density, i.e. a force or acceleration holding more particles at one place than another. This suggests a spatial resolution is linked with force.

We try to apply this idea to the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. " p " represents a constant momentum i.e. no acceleration, but $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are x distributions. This seems like a contradiction. One may bypass it by arguing that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which is the physical spatial density, but it does not contain relevant information such as direction of motion and momentum. Thus we focus on $\exp(ipx)$. It contains two dimensions to describe the direction of motion, but we speculate the two distributions suggest an action/reaction force with a $+p$ and $-p$ having the opposite reaction. Thus adding $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ yields $2\cos(px)$ i.e. a distribution associated with a resolution \hbar/p and a force/acceleration. $\exp(ipx)$ contains action and reaction so on average it may be associated with nonaccelerating motion i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$.

We argue one may extend this idea to a Newtonian bound state where dt (for fixed dx) measures the probability at x . If there is a correlation i.e. dt has the same value at two x points then in order to distinguish these two, the probability should be different at all x points in between, i.e. there should exist an x probability distribution, and hence acceleration. Thus we suggest that acceleration/force seems to be intimately connected with probabilities of a variable linked to spatial correlations. This may be a scalar kinetic energy of a particle as in an MB gas, or $\exp(ipx)$ where p and x are correlated in such a way as to create an internal ruler spacing of \hbar/p .

References

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